

SIMILARITY AND MULTIPLE MEANING IN MOTHER TONGUE CLASSES

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Annotation: As students become more independent, they will be able to work independently on the exercise. Another factor is the ability to make connections between exercises in the classroom. The relevance of the material to the topic and the purpose of the lesson will ensure that it is goal-oriented. All teaching materials used in the lesson (including those selected for language observation, spelling, and speaking exercises) should be appropriate to the purpose of the lesson.

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The accuracy and intrinsic logic of the lesson, its purposefulness, to some extent, led to the interaction of the logic of the lesson in which the new material is taught, the language phenomenon being studied, and its linguistic essence. It is important for the teacher to be aware of this interaction and to open it slowly as he or she completes assignments with students.

If the lesson aims to strengthen grammatical knowledge and spelling skills, the logical conditions of the lesson reflect a system of exercises that are gradually becoming more complex. One or two exercises are done collectively so that children can learn a spelling rule well. As students become more independent, they will be able to work independently. Another factor is the ability to make connections between exercises in the classroom. The relevance of the material to

the topic and the purpose of the lesson will ensure that it is goal-oriented. All teaching materials used in the lesson (including those selected for language observation, spelling, and speaking exercises) should be appropriate to the purpose of the lesson.

Speech development instruction in mother tongue lessons requires the use of methodological methods in teaching grammatical material so that students learn the role of each word group or part of speech in our language, i.e. grammar theory are taught to apply in practice the formation of fluent and clear speech skills, the development of comprehension and comprehension skills. Improving children's speech in the classroom is reflected in the content of the lesson and the types of tasks used in the lesson.

Words in a language have different relationships depending on their form and meaning. Some words are similar in form, some in meaning, and some in pronunciation. According to these characteristics, words are divided into the following groups:

1. Homonyms
2. Synonyms (synonyms)
3. Antonyms (words with opposite meanings)
4. Paronyms (pronunciation words)

Homonyms (Greek words homos) are words that have the same pronunciation and spelling but different meanings: yuz (horse) - face (number), mulberry (tree) - mulberry (movement).

Homonyms are divided into one word group (age - tears, age - measure of life), two different word groups (hungry - open the stomach: quality, open - open the door: verb), three different words also belongs to the z category (love - love game: horse, lover - haste: verb, lover - more: adjective; hur - heavenly hurries: horse, hur - free: adjective, hur - dog hurdi: verb) it can. Homonymy within a category is

found mainly in nouns and verbs. Words like this will keep you alive even when you take supplements.

Attention! No matter how many meanings there are, these meanings are interconnected. Because homonyms are different words, there is no connection between their meanings. Polysemous words are formed when a word is used in its own and figurative senses. Pronouns are two or more words that have the same shape.

When the connection between the meanings of plural words is broken, I am created: day - sun (main meaning); day - the bright part of the day illuminated by the sun (figurative meaning); dam - breath (own ma '.), dam - baskan (mobile ma '.), dam - rest (nom. ma '.); blue - color (own ma '.), blue - sky (nom. ma '.), speech - unity of speech and language (own ma '.), speech - banquet (ko'. chma ma '.).

Now these words are mutually beneficial.

There are the following types of homonyms:

1) Lexical homonyms are homonyms between words. Hair is a member, hair is movement, white is color, white is movement.

2) Phraseological homonyms are homonyms between phrases, that is, figurative, effective compounds: to raise one's head - to honor, to raise one's head - to make a fuss.

3) There are two types of grammatical homonyms:

a) morphological homonyms homonymy between affixes: full table (quality maker) - crop (horse maker); The synonyms of suffixes and auxiliaries are also morphological, that is, grammatical synonyms: went to school - went to school.)

b) Syntactic homonyms occur between phrases or sentences: homonymy of phrases: to be surprised by a lie (to be surprised by a lie) - to be surprised by a lie (lie to be amazed at the moment). The truth of the matter: Did my brother

Karimjon come? "Karimjon, is my brother here?"

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